

Synthesis of Steroidal Extranucleo N-Phenyloxazolidones of Androstane Series

A. H. SIDDIQUI*, K. VENKATESHWER RAO and K. VIJAYASENA REDDY

Department of Chemistry, Nizam College, Hyderabad-500 001

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17-Oxo-5-androsten-3 β -yl acetate (1a) and 3 β -chloro-17-oxo-5-androstene (2a) on reaction with hydrazine hydrate in alcoholic solution gave 5-androsten-17-hydrazone-3 β -yl acetate (1b) and 3 β -chloro-5-androsten-17-hydrazone (2b), respectively. The subsequent reaction of these 17-hydrazones (1b, 2b) with phenyl isocyanate in benzene solution afforded the corresponding 17-N-phenylsemicarbazone derivatives (1c, 2c), whose cyclisation with chloroacetic acid in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate and acetic acid yielded 20,21-diazo-5-androsten-21-(N-phenyl-1',3'-oxazolin-4'-one)-3 β -yl acetate (3a) and 3 β -chloro-20,21-diazo-5-androsten-21-(N-phenyl-1',3'-oxazolin-4'-one) (4a), respectively.

OXAZOLIDONES have been found to possess a variety of pharmacological and biological activities¹. In view of these useful biological activities, we have undertaken the preparation of steroidal oxazolidones.

1a; R=OAc, X=O
2a; R=Cl, X=O
1b; R=OAc, X=NNH₂
2b; R=Cl, X=NNH₂
1c; R=OAc, X=NNHC(=O)NHPH
2c; R=Cl, X=NNHC(=O)NHPH

3a, R=OAc
4a, R=Cl

3b; R=OAc
4b; R=Cl

17-Oxo-5-androsten-3 β -yl acetate (1a) and 3 β -chloro-17-oxo-5-androstene² (2a) were converted to the corresponding 17-hydrazone (1b, 2b), whose ir spectrum gave significant peaks at 3 300, 3 200 (NH₂) and 1 400, 1 410 cm⁻¹ (C=N).

The compound (1b, 2b) on treatment with phenyl isocyanate gave the respective 17-N-phenylsemicarbazones (1c, 2c) whose ir spectrum gave significant peaks at 3 400 (NH), 1 715 (C=O) and 1 650–1 400 cm⁻¹ (Ar). The cyclisation of (1c, 2c) with chloroacetic acid in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate and acetic acid furnished the product, which could be either (3a, 4a) or (3b, 4b). The characterisation of the product as 20,21-diazo-

5-androsten-21-(N-phenyl-1',3'-oxazolin-4'-one) (3a) and 3 β -chloro-20,21-diazo-5-androsten-21-(N-phenyl-1',3'-oxazolin-4'-one) (4a), respectively, rather than (3b, 4b) were based on spectral data, $\nu_{\max}$ 1 715 (C=O of oxazolidone), 1 650–1 400 (Ar) and 1 420 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ 7.3 (3H, t, Ar), 8.4 (2H, d, Ar), 4.5 (br, $W_{1/2}$ 12 Hz, 3 α -H), 5.25 (2H, s, CH₂ of oxazolidone). The conclusive evidence in support of structure 3a, 4a is afforded by ¹³C nmr spectral data. The product gave significant peaks at δ 220 (C=O of oxazolidone), 158.4 (C=N), 140.8 (C₆ olefinic), 129.2–118.7 (aromatic) and 73.2 (CH₂ of oxazolidone). The alternate structures (3b, 4b) would have given ¹³C nmr peaks of CH₂ of oxazolidone at δ 90.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian A60 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and ¹³C nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a JEOL JNN FX-100 (25.00 MHz) spectrometer with order FT Lock, internal deuterium in the solvent temperature 25°, using TMS as internal standard. Petroleum ether refers to a fraction of b.p. 60–80°. Analytical and physical data of the compounds are given in Table I.

17-Hydrazones (1b, 2b): The ketones (1a, 2a; 1.75 g) were refluxed with freshly distilled hydrazine hydrate (1 ml) in ethanolic solution (35 ml) in presence of acetic acid (1 drop) for 2 h. After usual work up the products were crystallised from ethanol to give the corresponding 17-hydrazones (1b, 2b) as colorless crystalline solids.

N-Phenylsemicarbazones (1c, 2c): To 1b/2b (1.5 g) in benzene (50 ml) was added phenyl isocyanate (2.5 ml) and the mixture refluxed on a water-bath for 3 h. The excess benzene was removed by

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Analysis % · Found/(Calcd.)		
			O	H	N
1b	145	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₂	79.24 (78.25)	9.26 (9.80)	8.08 (8.18)
2b	180-81	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ N ₃ Cl	71.04 (71.18)	9.03 (9.04)	8.67 (8.73)
1c	136-38	C ₂₀ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₂	72.56 (72.57)	7.90 (7.99)	9.01 (9.07)
2c	150-52	C ₂₀ H ₂₇ N ₃ OCl	70.91 (70.98)	7.70 (7.73)	9.54 (9.55)
3a	238-39	C ₂₀ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₂	71.50 (71.57)	7.84 (7.85)	8.88 (8.84)
4a	108-09	C ₂₀ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₂ Cl	70.01 (70.07)	7.08 (7.09)	8.79 (8.75)

distillation and the concentrated solution was cooled to obtain a crystalline solid (1c, 2c) which was washed with water and recrystallised from alcohol.

N-Phenyloxazolidone (3a, 4a): To 1c/2c (1 g) in acetic acid (35 ml) were added chloroacetic acid (0.25 g) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.35 g) and the mixture was refluxed for 7 h. Usual work up

afforded a compound, which was chromatographed over neutral alumina (30 g). Elution with petroleum ether gave the unreacted compound (1c, 2c) and further elution with benzene afforded the product (3a, 4a).

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